

Dr. Interested Research Proposal competition

Topic Title: *TMAO, A Gut Microbiome Derived Metabolite, and its Contribution to the Development of Cardiovascular Disease (CVD)*

Research Problem Question: “Do elevated trimethylamine N-oxide (*TMAO*) levels contribute to CVD in humans, and how effective are interventions (dietary, pharmaceutical or lifestyle) in reducing CVD risk markers and lowering *TMAO* levels?”

1. Executive Summary and Background

1.1 The Gut Microbiome

The GM is a complex ecosystem residing in Gastrointestinal tracts of animals plays a critical role in metabolizing dietary compounds and producing metabolites such as trimethylamine N-oxide (*TMAO*). The metabolite which is primarily focused in the review *TMAO*, is derived from dietary precursors such as *choline* and *L-carnitine*, mostly found in red-meat and dairy products. When these nutrients are primarily broken down by the GM, they form *TMA*, which is then oxidized in liver by *FMO3* enzyme [14].

1.2 Mechanisms of *TMAO*

Elevated levels of *TMAO* are mostly related to the increase in foam cell [7,11] formation

and closely linked with epithelial dysfunction [11], inflammation [7] and platelet activation [4] releasing coagulants such as thrombosis. Most importantly, meta-analysis reports that increases levels of *TMAO* can lead to a 62% increased risk of major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE) [32,33].

1.3 Format of Research

This proposal will be mainly in the form of a systematic literature review, including an Abstract, methodology, hypothesis, considerations and limitations. This will be achieved by considering and evaluating interventions such as pharmaceutical medications, dietary changes and moderations in regular physical activity levels.

1.4 Gaps and Aim

Certain irregularities in current researches and studies include diversity in dietary patterns (omnivores/non-veg vs. vegetarians), the role of genetics and the renal functionality on *TMAO* levels.

The aim is to assess and evaluate whether reducing *TMAO* can aid in mitigating cardiovascular events, and perhaps even serve as a predictor or biomarker which will result in improved global long term outcomes.

2. Abstract

Background: Cardiovascular disease (CVD) undoubtedly remains as the most fatal disease, being the leading cause of mortality worldwide, with atherosclerosis as one of its most widely accepted drivers. Traditional risk factors such as hypertension, dyslipidemia, diabetes, and inflammation explain much of the origin, however, with emerging evidence, it is impossible to undermine the gut microbiota as a critical, underexplored determinant of cardiovascular health. In particular, the gastrointestinal resultant metabolite trimethylamine N-oxide (*TMAO*), a product of gut microbiota assimilated by its dietary precursors including *choline*, *phosphatidylcholine*, and *L-carnitine*. Following the absorption of pre-mentioned precursors, they are broken down into *TMA* (Trimethylamine). After the assimilation of *TMA* in the circulatory system, it becomes oxidized into *TMAO* in the hepatic system by catalytic enzymes hepatic flavin monooxygenases (*FMO*'s). This relatively new groundbreaking discovery has put *TMAO* up on the podium along with other CVD factors, due to its direct close relation in the progression of atherosclerosis. Elevated *TMAO* levels are associated with endothelial dysfunction, foam cell formation [5,7,11] (due to its effects on macrophages), enhanced platelet hyperreactivity, and increased thrombus formation, thereby accelerating a myriad of CVD including increased risks of plaque instability, vascular dysfunction, Myocardial infarction, stroke and arrhythmia.

Objectives: This review will utilize current evidence on the mechanistic links between *TMAO* and atherosclerosis progression, drawing on both animal and human studies, and will critically evaluate dietary intercessions such as consuming a more MD (Mediterranean

diet), microbial, and pharmacological interventions—including probiotics, enzyme inhibitors such as *FMO3* blockers, and natural compounds like berberine. (BBR), as well as lifestyle changes in exercise by assimilating more aerobic workouts in one's daily routine. By integrating findings across metabolic, immunological, and cardiovascular pathways, the project aims to clarify whether *TMAO* represents a causal mediator or a biomarker of disease, and to identify therapeutic strategies that could mitigate its contribution to cardiovascular risk.

Methods: This review is conducted as a systematic literature review, with no direct human analysis, utilizing databases such as PubMed, NIH, ScienceDirect, WHO, the New England Journal of Medicine (NEJM), and Google Scholar for cross-checking. Inclusion criteria comprised peer-reviewed human and animal studies measuring plasma *TMAO* levels in relation to CVD outcomes, dietary precursors, and interventional strategies. Non-peer-reviewed sources were excluded. Findings were compared across studies with varying population sizes, control conditions, and study durations, with the strength and consistency of associations considered throughout.

Results and Conclusion: Elevated plasma *TMAO* levels have been consistently associated with a range of cardiovascular pathways — platelet hyperreactivity, endothelial dysfunction, impaired reverse cholesterol transport, and systemic vascular inflammation —all of which collectively accelerate the risks of atherosclerosis as well as the progression of a range of diseases like myocardial infarction, ischemic stroke, cardiac arrhythmia, and

heart failure [1,2,5,25,26]. It is evident in many reports that elevated TMAO levels can increase the risk of major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE) [32,33]. Interventions such as dietary modifications, regular exercise, clinical probiotic supplementation or enzyme inhibitors such as berberine demonstrate significant reductions in *TMAO* levels and associated CVD markers [12,14,22,23]. *TMAO*'s function as a biomarker [5] is equally important, as it allows researchers and doctors alike to not only lessen the effects and demonstrate the progression of a range of diseases like stroke, MI, AF, Sudden Cardiac Death [1,2,13,18,25,26], and even HIV, but also indicates its evident potential to be used as a biomarker of other major diseases like colorectal cancer, by finding relevant correlations and extensive testing. Despite this, the precise causal role of *TMAO* in atherosclerosis remains debated, and the impact of interventions targeting its production or alleviating its effects is not fully defined. However, the majority of data-backed research supports its role in both accelerating CVD and acting as an invaluable prognostic biomarker.

3. Research Objectives

- To compare prevalent and existing clinical studies measuring blood plasma *TMAO* and CVD outcomes such as inflammation of the ganglionated Plexi, atherosclerosis progression, endothelial dysfunction, eventually leading to major CVD such as HF (heart failure) and MI

- To compare *TMAO* levels across dietary precursors/patterns (*choline/carnitine*; omnivore vs Mediterranean/plant-based) and relate these to plasma levels of *TMAO*,
- To evaluate the effectiveness and reliability of interventions (probiotics, prebiotics, exercise, short-term antibiotics, enzyme inhibitors including berberine, *FMO* blockers) on *TMAO* reduction and in alleviating its effects and production
- To evaluate the potential of *trimethylamine N-oxide* (*TMAO*) as a biomarker for cardiovascular disease and other general systemic conditions.

4.0 Research Questions:

- By what mechanisms does *TMAO* promote atherothrombosis—specifically platelet hyperreactivity, endothelial dysfunction, macrophage ox-LDL uptake/foam cell formation, and altered cholesterol handling?
- How do dietary precursors (*phosphatidylcholine, choline, L-carnitine*) and diet patterns (omnivorous vs. Mediterranean/plant-forward) influence *TMAO* levels and illustrate cardiovascular risk markers?
- Which interventions (dietary change, probiotics/prebiotics, short-term antibiotics, enzyme inhibitor, increase in physical exercises) most effectively lower *TMAO* and/or improve vascular/platelet endpoints, and how durable are these effects after discontinuation?

- Can *TMAO* possibly act as a biomarker and predictor for CVD compared to traditional risk factors and whether it can evidently help in producing a timeline of the disease and its prognosis?

5. Literature Review

5.1 Mechanisms of *TMAO* in Cardiovascular Disease (CVD)

Recent research has established the central role of *trimethylamine N-oxide (TMAO)* in the pathogenesis of cardiovascular disease. One of the most critical mechanisms is its contribution to platelet hyperreactivity [4,18]. *TMAO* actively accentuates platelet sensitivity by enhancing receptor responsiveness to thrombin [4], thereby requiring significantly less stimulation for activation and fibrinogen release. Usually, platelet activation requires an external stimulus to the receptors, which in turn release fibrinogen, which is converted to insoluble fibrin monomers by thrombin. However, since the function of platelets is amplified as such by *TMAO*, even in the absence of such external stimuli — it can trigger the release of thrombin. Furthermore, deeper studies have found a direct positive correlation between *TMAO* and increased intracellular Ca^{2+} release from storage sites in the platelet [4,18,30], which is needed for enhanced reactivity and activation. Therefore, this promotes stronger platelet aggregation and a more robust clot formation. In certain mice studies [4,13], researchers have associated elevated *TMAO* levels with the acceleration of both arterial and venous thrombosis, whilst in human anatomic studies,

plasma *TMAO* are more likely to be biomarkers [5] for future CVD events, independent of traditional risk factors and symptoms.

Moreover, hyperreactive platelets [4,30] expose more phosphatidylserine, which accelerates the conversion of prothrombin to thrombin. Dietary precursors of *TMAO*, such as *choline*, have been shown to intensify responses to the agonist adenosine diphosphate (ADP) [3], strengthening the direct link between *TMAO* levels and platelet function. These changes result in increased thrombus formation, even in the absence of vascular injury.

5.11 Contribution of Diet and Gut Microbiota (GM) in TMAO Production

Correlation	Source	Population (N)	Duration	Primary Outcome (Δ TMAO)	Durability / Limitations
Positive	Barrea et al. (2019)	144 healthy adults	-	Higher levels in men ($P < 0.0001$); lower adherence to Mediterranean Diet in men ($P = 0.017$)	Lower adherence in males affects results ⁴ .
Positive	Bernstein (2010)	84,136 Women (Ages 30–55)	26 Years	High red meat intake associated with 952 CVD deaths; 1 serving of nuts = 30% lower risk	Chronic effect over long-term follow-up ⁵ .
Positive	Sinha et al. (2009)	322,263 Men / 223,390 Women	10 Years	71,252 total deaths; high red/processed meat intake linked to increased mortality	Massive sample size; specific to red meat ⁶ .
Positive	Papandreu et al. (2020)	20 Adult humans	24 Weeks	Oral ingestion of L-carnitine significantly increases risk of TMAO	Changes in biomarkers only discovered after 24 weeks.
Positive	Jeong et al 2019	Human patients	31	Oral administration of l-carnitine causes elevated TMAO levels	Increased TMAO levels may be beneficial for vascular damage in HD patients.
Negative	Zang et al. (2022)	Human volunteers	-	Significantly increased TMAO levels after fish consumption	Conflicting: Fish intake raises TMAO but reduces CVD risk via Omega-3 ⁷ .
Negative	Manhaes et al. (2025)	14 human participants	4 Days	No significant difference in TMAO post red meat ($P=0.21$) or fish ($P=0.91$)	Very short duration (4 days) likely influenced lack of results.

Figure 1.

The TMAO-CVD Cascade

Figure 1. The TMAO-CVD Cascade: Figure 1 illustrates how dietary precursors are converted into TMAO, which in turn causes inflammation, endothelial dysfunction, platelet hyperreactivity, and impaired cholesterol transport. All these processes combined hasten thrombosis and atherosclerosis, which can result in clinical consequences like arrhythmias, heart failure, myocardial infarction, and stroke.

The gut microbiota plays an essential role in *TMAO* synthesis. However, dietary substrates play an equally crucial role, providing the *TMAO* precursors allowing the metabolization of *TMA* into *TMAO* subsequently. These substrates are rich in trimethylamine groups, notably *choline*, *phosphatidylcholine* and *L-carnitine* [1,3]. In the gastrointestinal metagenome, at least nine strains capable of converting *choline* into *trimethylamine (TMA)* have been identified. Moreover, dietary *L-carnitine*, another precursor, has been implicated in promoting atherosclerosis and elevating *TMAO* levels. Specific bacteria metabolize the previously mentioned nutrients into *TMA*, which goes onwards to the hepatic system to be oxidized by *FMO* enzymes in the liver to form *TMAO*.

However, while gut microbiota diversity plays a crucial role in metabolizing the diet leading to *TMAO*, certain foods including strains of fish contain *TMAO* in its raw form [14,16]. This means that they will increase *TMAO* levels regardless of the diversity of GM, and thus dietary intake consuming of the specified strains of fish can alone elevate plasma *TMAO*

levels, however, it is worth mentioning that fish also contain omega-3 FA's, which is found to lower the rate of mortality due to CVD [21], therefore the net response will depend on the strain on the fish.

5.12 TMAO and Endothelial Dysfunction

Endothelial dysfunction is another critical pathway influenced by *TMAO*, which indirectly is responsible for a range of CVD effects independent of other factors, such as atherosclerosis. Studies have demonstrated an inverse relationship between *TMAO* levels and endothelial function [5,9], such as reduced brachial artery flow-mediated dilation in elderly patients following *TMAO* supplementation. Furthermore, in experimentations on murine models, *TMAO* was found to increase oxidative stress [11,13,18,20,30] via superoxide production. However, a certain inhibitor, namely *3,3-Dimethyl-1-butanol* has been successful in regulating pro-inflammatory cytokine expression to pre-elevated *TMAO* amounts [11,30], while also mitigating oxidative stress by inhibiting *TMA-lyase* both in vitro and in vivo, which validates a therapeutic strategy for reducing *TMAO*-induced thrombosis.

5.13 TMAO and Inflammation & Immunity

In this mechanism used by *TMAO*, the superfluous inflammatory response involves upregulation of *SR-A1* and *CD36* expression genes in macrophage [29], enhancing the uptake of oxidized LDL and foam cell formation. Moreover, past its impact on macrophages, *TMAO* has been found to disrupt hepatic function, as it promotes bile acid secretion [18] and weakens reverse cholesterol transport, further intensifying plaque development, independent from the usual cholesterol-based atherosclerosis.

Additionally, *TMAO* elevates pro-inflammatory cytokine expression while suppressing anti-inflammatory cytokines. It also induces stress-inducible heat shock proteins (HSP) [30] such as *glucose-regulated protein 94*, which eventually leads to endoplasmic reticulum stress and exacerbating vascular inflammation.

5.14 *TMAO* and cholesterol transport

TMAO has been found to inhibit the RCT procedure, limiting the removal and transportation of excess cholesterol by macrophages. Reverse cholesterol transport (RCT) is a procedure in which excess accumulated cholesterol in the body, specifically in arteries, is reversed and reduced by certain macrophages. This is due to an imbalance in the healthy ratio of LDL's and HDL's, with the ideal being 3.5:1. However, anything above 5:1 increases the risk of developing CVD due to excess cholesterol deposits which can then in turn elevate the risk of clogged arteries and accentuate thrombosis formation, eventually leading to atherosclerosis. RCT has anti-atherosclerotic effects by regulating the flow of cholesterol.

5.15 *TMAO* as a double activator of CVD

As illustrated in fig. 1 which displays all the pre-mentioned mechanisms of *TMAO*, the evidence clearly illustrates that while *TMAO* promotes atherosclerosis formation due to Vascular Dysfunction, Foam Cell formation, as well as inhibiting macrophages by limiting their effects on removal of excess cholesterol, it also simultaneously increases the risk of the accumulated plaque to cause ruptured endothelial linings and clot formation through platelet hyperreactivity. This dual action mechanism of *TMAO* explains why it can act as such an effective marker for several CVD.

5.2 Interventions

Intervention Category	Study Source	Population (N)	Specific Treatment	Primary Outcome (Δ TMAO)	Clinical/Vascular Outcome	Durability (post-treatment)
Antibiotic Therapy	Tang et al. (2013)	40 Healthy adults	High-phosphatidylcholine diet + broad-spectrum antibiotics	Significant suppression of plasma TMAO after administration of broad-spectrum antibiotics	Suppression of TMA-producing intestinal microbiota	Levels returned to baseline levels after termination of antibiotic ingestion
Enzyme Inhibitors	Ma et al. (2022)	21 Atherosclerosis patients	0.5g oral Berberine (BBR)	Down-regulated Choline-TMA-TMAO pathway, decrease of 38 and 29% in feces ($P < 0.05$; $P < 0.05$), and 37 and 35% in plasma ($P < 0.001$; $P < 0.05$)	3.2% average reduction in atherosclerotic plaque	Observed over 4-month period
Probiotics	Qiu et al. (2018)	Murine microbial models	<i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i> ZDY04	Reduced serum TMAO and TMA levels by having effects on relevant gut microbiota families and NOT by lowering levels of	Improved gut microbial diversity	Mitigated TMAO by modulating gut bacteria and NOT by lowering expression of FMO3 and TMAO dietary precursors
Lifestyle/Exercise	Physical Activity Guidelines for Americans 2023	General Population	150 mins/week moderate-to-high intensity cardio	Lowered TMAO levels via GM diversification	Strengthened cardiomyocytes and cardiovascular health and general benefits of strengthening cardio aerobic respiration	Permanent if lifestyle is maintained

Figure 2.

Figure 2. Factors Influencing Plasma TMAO Levels

Fig. 2 summarizes Dietary, lifestyle, and microbiological factors that either raise or lower plasma TMAO levels. Risk-enhancing factors like red meat, eggs, dairy, and sedentary behavior are compared to protective factors like plant-based diets, probiotics, and regular exercise.

5.21 Dietary Modifications

As suggested by fig 2 above, reducing intake of *choline*, and carnitine-rich foods such as eggs, red meat, and dairy has been proven to lower *TMAO* production. Certain studies have found that a Mediterranean diet, characterized by low red meat and high fiber intake due to its richness in plant-based nutrition, fosters gut bacteria that do not produce *TMA*, thereby reducing *TMAO* levels [6,14] by diversifying the GM. Remarkably, a study based in Italy demonstrated that sex-based differences in *TMAO* concentrations - usually higher in men than women - justified the lower adherence to MD (Mediterranean Diet) by men [22]. Red meat consumption directly correlates with *TMAO* levels due to bacterial conversion of *carnitine* into *TMA*. *Phosphatidylcholine* is found to be the main risk factor of development of atherosclerosis, Heart Failure, and severe CVD. Therefore, reducing levels of *phosphatidylcholine*, found in egg yolks and soya beans plays a direct role in reducing *TMAO* and in turn lowers CVD risks.

Phytochemicals in plant-based diets evidently diversify and modulate the gut microbiome to reduce *TMAO* production, again, by suppressing *TMA* inducing bacteria. For instance, *Alisma orientalis*, traditionally consumed as an anti-atherosclerotic drink, has been shown to reduce *TMAO* via gut microbiota modulation and decreased expression of hepatic *FMO3* enzymes [1,14]. A comparative study over four weeks investigating individuals ingesting HFD (high-fat diet) and LFD along with MD found that there were significantly elevated *TMAO* levels in the prior [2].

5.22 Probiotics and Prebiotics

The intake of probiotic strains such as *Lactobacillus plantarum* and *Bifidobacterium longum*, found in fermented foods like pickles and olives, have been shown to suppress *TMA*-producing bacteria and promote beneficial microbial populations [17,22]. It is certainly reliable therefore, that probiotics are considered so efficient, as in mice otherwise fed a *choline*-rich diet, *Lactobacillus plantarum* supplementation significantly reduced *TMAO* levels [22]. Prebiotics like inulin and *fructooligosaccharides* (FOS) similarly encourage the production of non-*TMA*-producing bacteria, aiding in the lowering of *TMAO* concentrations, though, indirectly [31].

5.23 Antibiotic Therapy

Short-term antibiotic use of certain antibiotics such as *rifaximin*, *ciprofloxacin*, and *metronidazole*, have demonstrated efficacy in reducing *TMAO*-producing bacteria [17]. This demonstrates that even though long-term antibiotic use for treatment may be a topic of debate, short-term use can provide targeted relief. In a study involving 40 healthy

participants on a high-*phosphatidylcholine* diet, broad-spectrum antibiotics led to reduced *TMAO* levels, although these levels returned to baseline post-treatment [2].

5.24 Physical Activity and Lifestyle Changes

Physical Activity, specifically aerobic exercise has been shown to diversify gut microbiota which in turn reduces certain *TMA*-producing bacteria [17]. Activities such as cycling and running not only lower *TMAO* levels but also strengthen overall cardiovascular health.

According to the 2023 Physical Activity Guidelines for Americans, at least 150 minutes of moderate to high-intensity cardio per week was encouraged to promote beneficial changes in microbiota composition [17].

5.25 Enzyme Inhibitors

Enzyme inhibitors such as *berberine* (*BBR*) have recently emerged as promising and effective methods in reducing *TMAO* levels [12]. The mechanism includes inhibiting *choline-TMA lyase* (*CutC*) and *flavin monooxygenase* (*FMO*) in the gut and liver, preventing the oxidation of *TMA* into *TMAO*. Research by Shu Rong Ma and his colleagues found out that oral *BBR*'s metabolite dihydroberberine played a significant role in interacting with the enzyme *CutC* and reducing *TMAO* levels via a vitamin-like effect. In the same study, 21 patients suffering with atherosclerosis showed a 3.2% average plaque reduction after a 0.5g dose of *BBR* over 4 months.

As previously mentioned, and in addition to berberine, *3,3-Dimethyl-1-butanol* has shown potential [14]. This compound not only inhibits *TMAO* formation in the GM, as well as normalizing inflammatory responses by regulating pro-inflammatory cytokines, but was

also successful in murine testing as it not only reduced oxidative stress in young mice but inhibited the formation of foam cells and ceased the progression of aortic root plaques [11].

6. Significance

Correlation	Source	Population (N)	Duration	Primary Outcome (Δ TMAO)	CVD Outcome	Durability / Limitations
Positive	Tang et al. (2014)	720 patients	-	TMAO independently predicted 3-fold higher mortality	Stable Heart Failure	Association with dormant heart failure.
Positive	Suzuki et al. (2017)	1079 patients	2 Years	TMAO predicted death/MI at 2 years; superior to other biomarkers	Acute Myocardial Infarction (MI)	High predictive accuracy at 2-year mark.
Positive	Schiattarella et al. (2017)	26,167 (Meta-analysis)	-	All-cause mortality increased by 7.6% per 10 μ mol/L increment	General CVD Mortality	Distribution in general population unknown.
Positive	Farhangi et al. (2020)	1,622 adults	-	Relevant correlation between circulating TMAO and death	High risk of mortality	Data was reported as incomplete.
Negative	Mueller et al. (2015)	339 patients	8 Years	Plasma levels not related to MI or CHD history	Suspected Coronary Artery Disease (CAD)	Study found no relation over 8-year follow-up.
Negative	Amarasekera et al. (2019)	1,879 human adults with HF	-	TMAO and L-carnitine levels not associated with cases	Heart Failure (HF)	Only considered a single population.

6.1 Understanding severity of CVD

To fully understand the significance of *TMAO* in not only clinical research, but also its disease-causing nature, one must understand that cardiovascular disease (CVD) is the leading cause of death worldwide. As reported by the World Health Organization (WHO), an estimated 19.8 million people died from CVDs only in 2022, this accounts for nearly 32% of all global deaths. To put this into perspective, 85% of deaths were due to heart attacks and strokes, which, as mentioned above, are the clear consequence of constant thrombosis and an increase in *TMAO* levels [15]. In addition to that, CVD including Heart Failure, coronary artery disease, atherosclerosis, aneurysm, thrombosis and hypertension [5,19] are not-only economic, but also social and place great communal burden and an ever-prevalent threat to human health.

6.2 TMAO plays a pivotal role in accelerating many forms of CVD

In light with recent research, gut microbiota has been found to play a pivotal role in contributing to metabolic and cardiovascular disorders. The GM secretes metabolites which participate in the maintenance of cardiovascular homeostasis, and disturbing this fragile balance can directly influence progression of CVD. Furthermore, further exploring *TMAO*, we find that it is not only a lead factor or atherosclerosis, but also a range of other CVD events such as MI, stroke and HF [1,2,5,25,26,30].

6.21 Myocardial Infarction

One of the more severe ones, Myocardial infarction, happens when the heart's blood supplying arteries are blocked. Some of the causes of blockage in arteries include atherosclerosis, hypertension and diabetes. Moreover, these can not only clog the blood supply but also induce damage to cardiomyocytes. Even though a direct relation between *TMAO* and MI hasn't been found, it is simply observatory; as previously mentioned, *TMAO* is the leading cause of oxidation-based stress in mice and atherosclerosis in humans, which in turn cause MI [2,11,13]. Moreover, people with elevated *TMAO* levels have shown in studies that they lack the ability to grow and repair normal levels of cardiomyocytes; therefore, they are more likely to have another MI. However, this relationship can be majorly useful in an effective way, by being utilized as a biomarker, effectively reducing the effects of MI along with showing the prognosis of MI suffering individuals [5].

6.22 Stroke

Stroke is caused by either a blocked artery cutting off the supply of blood to the brain, or hemorrhage-based stroke, which is when a blood vessel in the brain ruptures. For the sake of the research in question, we will discuss the prior. According to research, *TMAO* is thought to be a pathogenic metabolite which causes hypertension, along with amplifying the renin-angiotensin systems effect. Moreover, it is also a lead factor of ischemic stroke [1,2,5,25,26], causing vascular dysfunction. Studies have found that hypertension causes the gut blood barrier to increase in permeability, which allowed the induction of *TMA* in the

bloodstream and therefore raise the quantity and risk of increased levels of *TMAO*, repeating the cycle.

6.23 Cardiac Arrhythmia

Arrhythmias is when the heartbeat is irregular, due to the electrical impulses which the heart uses to pump, don't work properly. Studies have once again shown that *TMAO* leads to an increase in the human bodies regulated electrical remodeling and inflammation of the ganglionated Plexi, which speed up the risk of arrhythmias. *TMAO* can also accelerate autonomous remodeling by affecting the p65 NF- κ B signaling pathway [27]. Furthermore, increased *TMAO* levels have been found to prevent cardiac mitochondria from oxidizing fatty acids, slowing down metabolism [28].

7. Justification

7.1 Clinical Potential as a biomarker for CVD

Multiple clinical studies have proven the fact that most patients with CVD related diseases such as heart arrhythmia, HF (heart failure), strokes have remarkably higher levels of blood Plasma *TMAO* level [1,2,14,18,27]. This proposes substantial implications for disease prevention and predicting prognosis of the CVD, saving millions of lives worldwide. This is due to *TMAO*'s potential ability to be utilized to predict clinical risk and long-term indication for AS and CVD, as it can serve as a biomarker for Atherosclerosis [5], thus, potentially limiting the disease progression and reversing CHD as the number one deadly disease worldwide. Data in a recent study in 2010 by Bernstein evidently shows from a

follow-up of more than 84,000 women over 26 years who had consistent high intakes of red meat (containing *choline*, leading dietary factor of *TMAO*) significantly elevated the risk of coronary heart disease (CHD). Similarly, in an investigation of 300 CHD patients by Zhong et al. in 2010, it was found that plasma concentrations of metabolites such as *TMAO*, *choline*, and creatinine were highly notable in a person suffering from CHD, justifying the previously mentioned studies as well. If we want to look at an even more reliable and experimentally unwavering study, we can find that in Yu et al. in 2019, while investigating 275 patients with CHD and 275 control, it was discovered that urinary *TMAO* may have been the cause of the development of CHD.

7.12 *TMAO* Biomarker for HIV and Carotid Plaques

Beyond regular cardiovascular implications, recent evidences illustrate that *TMAO*'s ability to be a biomarker is not limited to CVD's, but a successful one in other major diseases as well. In a research by Shan et al. in 2018, 520 patients infected with HIV were surprisingly found to have enhanced levels of *TMAO* showed increased risk of carotid plaques. The clinical severity of this finding is highly noteworthy, as severe high-grade plaque could mean an average of 34% mortality rate.

7.13 *TMAO* as biomarker for Heart Failure and MI

Another study in Tang et al. in 2014 found that increased plasma levels of *TMAO* were directly associated with dormant heart failure, enhancing the mortality rate by more than 3-fold [35]. Moreover, looking at a more severe heart condition, a study by Suzuki et al. in

2017 showed that in more than 1000 patients suffering from acute Myocardial infarction, *TMAO* independently predicted death from MI at 2 years, already much more accurate to previously used biomarkers.

Therefore, a wider focus of experimental and data-backed research for *TMAO* as a biomarker is pivotal. As we have already discussed, mentioning multiple studies, the use of *TMAO* as a biomarker is nothing short of a successful and effective biomarker for diseases, not limiting to just CVD and AS, but rather other ones such as HF and HIV. This illustrates the possibility of the utilization of this metabolite to predict the progression of a variety of other possible diseases, such as the likes of cancer and even neurodegenerative disorder [18], which is justified by the already present mechanism *TMAO* causing ganglionated Plexi inflammation in the heart. As for cancer, *TMAO* is already emerging as an evident not only forecaster, but also its possible role as a carcinogen in colorectal cancer [10] due to its mechanisms relating to oxidative stress, DNA damage and protein misfolding [18]. Most importantly though, its use as a primary predictor for atherosclerosis perpetually remains, as according to studies, 1 in 3 people die globally due to AS related illnesses [36].

8. Methodology

8.1 Type of study and keywords included

This review will include a systematic Literature review (no direct human analysis) utilizing databases such as PubMed, NIH, ScienceDirect, WHO, New England Journal of Medicine

(NEJM) and Google Scholar (for cross checking). The keywords and search terms will primarily focus on basic imperative metabolite terms: “*TMAO* and atherosclerosis”, “gut microbiome and cardiovascular disease”, along with dietary terms including “*choline*”, “carnitine”, “*phosphatidylcholine*”, “L-carnitine”. Moreover, the *TMAO* mechanism terms will include “foam cell formation”, “*TMAO* and inflammation”, “platelet hyperreactivity *TMAO*”, “thrombin”, “endothelial dysfunction”, “DNA damage”. And lastly, the Intervention terms: “dietary intervention *TMAO*”, “probiotics *Lactobacillus TMAO*”, “enzyme inhibitors *TMAO*”, “berberine BBR *TMAO*”, “Antibiotics and *TMAO*”, “Lifestyle changes *TMAO*”

8.2 Inclusion and exclusion criteria:

The inclusion criteria include peer-reviewed human or animal - especially murine- studies or models of different mechanisms of atherosclerosis and main regions of effects of *TMAO*, specifically in accelerating CVD, by measuring its plasma levels of in accordance with precursor metabolites, which will be mostly based on trial-backed articles.

Interventional studies testing diet/probiotics/enzymes also ought to be crucially considered.

Exclusion Criteria include sources such as non-peer reviewed research articles. Moreover, we will compare findings across different studies and data ranges, considering studies with and without control of populations, considering the strength and justification of associations and concluded results

9. Ethical Considerations

In line with ethical and moral considerations, no primary human subjects were directly studied due to risk of violation of patient integrity, secondary data only, which includes a vast number of individuals and/or volunteers for research purposes or studies done on a vast majority of a population, without putting at risk the integrity of individual patients. As for the sourcing, ethically sourced, peer-reviewed and verified sources only will be used, without any major or defining conflict of interest, whilst clearly acknowledging if there is any.

9.1 Contextualized data

It is essential that all experimental data and reviews in articles is backed up by context, as it is crucial to provide background, as to not humiliate certain disease populations mentioned, for e.g.: HIV, CHD patients and HFD, LFD diets. In addition to that, we will highlight and make sure that future interventions (for e.g. antibiotics) must balance efficiency with risks of resistance, negative auto-immune response and safety, while considering the long-debated use of the lasting use of antibiotics in response to the ever-growing concern of antibiotic resistance. Lastly, all sources must be cross verified with other databases to prevent misinformation and to minimize conflict of interest.

10. Expected Results

10.1 Mechanisms

This review is anticipated to acknowledge and confirm the findings related to mechanism or *TMAO*, such as its role in higher platelet activity, resulting in higher risk of thrombosis, along with the mechanisms of endothelial dysfunction, vascular damage and inflammation and causes impairment to the regular electrical signals in cardiomyocytes. It is also expected to find that *TMAO* induces plaque burden by modulating the normal reverse cholesterol action of the body

10.2 Dietary precursors

As for dietary influence, omnivorous and non-veg diet (such as red meat, dairy products) may lead to increased levels of the metabolite due to their richness in the dietary precursors of *TMAO* like *choline* and carnitine. On that note, it is expected that diet rich in plant-based nutrients in comparison would not be as *TMAO* inducing, perhaps even relating to reduced levels of *TMAO*

10.3 Intervention

While it is important to consider the medical side of trial based cures such as probiotic and drug interventions which may lower *TMAO* by altering with the gut microbiota and suppress the formation of *TMAO*, it is also important to note that regular physical activity is directly related to better cardiovascular health, by reducing the heartrate and strengthening the cardiomyocytes. Moreover, positive effects of physical activity are not only limited to that,

since it induces discipline and consistency in one's life, which could be utilized for other things such as avoiding non-balanced diets.

11. Limitations

11.1 Dietary role of fish

It has also been found that some dietary nourishments confounding from fish/seafood can elevate levels of *TMAO* regardless of microbial conversion. In a study by Zang and colleagues in 2022, it was discovered that *TMAO* levels were significantly increased in volunteers after consumption of fish related products.

However, in some studies, such as by Kromhout et al. in 1985, fish were interestingly found to lower risks of CVD. It is important to note that this is not due to the raw *TMAO* present, but rather the omega-3 content which counteracts the CVD risks. Therefore, the net results can vary depending on the strain of fish, its raw average *TMAO* and omega-3 content.

Furthermore, some fish were also found to contain strains of cardioprotective inducing metabolites, such as omega- polyunsaturated acids, like docosahexaenoic acid (DHA).

Newly investigated research of around 191,000 individuals showcased that regular fish consumption weekly is directly related to decreasing CVD risks in patients with prior CVD, as mentioned by Mitchel L. Zoler in 2021 in his article, Eating Fish Tied to Fewer CVD Events in High-Risk People.

Therefore, in order to consider this and still measure more accurate plasma *TMAO* levels, one can differentiate the diets between individuals during research, such as analyzing already proven *TMAO* inducing foods such as red meat separate from fish driven *TMAO*.

11.2 Different Clinical and physical viewpoints

Mechanistic vs clinical endpoints could infrequently mismatch (in vivo and vitro). Clinical patient-based vs lab research often might show limited correlation relating to *TMAO* mechanisms of *TMAO*, such as demonstrated in Zhu et al in 2016. Moreover, some research has different opinions regarding the effects of *TMAO* itself, however, this is mostly not the cause. In a study done by Koay et al. 2021, it was suggested that even though specific dietary interventions have been successful in decreasing levels of plasma *TMAO*, it is uncertain that the elevated levels are related to build up of atherosclerosis, but rather increased plaque instability [8].

To address this, one can separate mechanical proof from clinical patient based prognostic data. Moreover, instead of negatively comparing them, one can use the clinical laboratory results as base standard values and compare the progression of *TMAO* in human based clinical research by comparing them to the set values. Lastly, as for different viewpoints, one must consider the variety of studies with experimental-backed data, as it is rarely the case where the opinion goes against the vast majority of articles, however, it is important to regard both perspectives, specifically because considering atherosclerosis is a type of plaque build-up. Therefore, both sides should be included to be compared and contrasted to ultimately derive at a more balanced review.

11.3 Short-term durability of intervention affects, such as probiotics and antibiotics.

During the set time of dosage, it is evident that certain antibiotics suppress *TMAO* but rebound after the termination of the dosage. To mitigate this, follow up extractions are pivotal, along with post-discontinuation trajectories and commenting on the adherence of the antibiotics, as it is not unusual for patients to discontinue their prescribed antibiotics beforehand. By conducting post dose termination observations such as this, we can find out which specific doses of what antibiotics must be given for how much time, until the post-discontinuation observations show no recoiling of plasma *TMAO* levels.

One can also use this data to intertwine certain dietary and enzyme targeted approaches during the later stage of, or during post discontinuation of the antibiotic/probiotic to observe the efficiency of certain interventions in sustainably reducing *TMAO* levels in plasma, even after antibiotic suspension. Therefore, long term longitudinal human studies are needed to compare with lab studies to confirm causation, rather than just correlation.

11.4 Gut Microbial diversity in populations

Considering microbial diversity is vital, as can be affected by a variety of factors including geography of population, along with sex and cultural diets and lifestyle choices. Therefore, populations must not be generalized and data from each should be studied individually.

We must also utilize diverse samplings, such as in different populations based on ethnicity, omni/vegetarian diet, lifestyle conditions, and report values of plasma levels with each diverse population to observe correlations, or whether it is just the dietary culture which affects the microbial diversity, leading to different levels of *TMAO*.

12. Conclusion

The evidence presented in this review undoubtedly supports the conclusion that *TMAO* is a significant contributor to CVD and its progression. By focusing particularly on four cardiovascular pathways — platelet hyperreactivity, endothelial dysfunction, decreased reverse cholesterol transport, and vascular inflammation — elevated *TMAO* plasma levels increase the risks of atherosclerosis and a wide range of other CVD events including myocardial infarction, ischemic stroke, and heart failure [1,2,4,5,7,11]. However, most notable is the fact that these mechanisms do not function by themselves in isolation; but rather, compound one another. This explains why elevated *TMAO* levels are such a universally reliable and consistent progression indicator for several CVD related risks.

As for interventions, it is important to note that in isolation, no single strategy offers a sustainable and complete solution. From a dietary perspective, a higher inclusion of a Mediterranean plant based diet remains the most widely suitable approach, given its ability to diversify the gut microbiota [14,22], which undoubtedly plays a crucial role in metabolizing certain dietary precursors, namely — choline, L-carnitine, and phosphatidylcholine — into TMA which is then subsequently converted into *TMAO*. Not only that, but a plant-based diet is generally suitable, considering it does not contain the specific metabolites previously mentioned which are usually only found in meat. Through a clinical perspective, evidence has suggested that enzyme inhibitors such as berberine and probiotic strains including *Lactobacillus plantarum* have not only shown significant reduction in *TMAO* levels, but also alleviate pre-existing CVD risks, such as atherosclerotic

plaque burden [12,23]. Furthermore, while short-term antibiotic therapy continues to play an effective role in mitigating TMAO's effects during administration, it is limited by post-discontinuation rebound of TMAO levels, alongside concerns regarding antibiotic resistance with prolonged use. Implementing regular aerobic exercise is also notable, as it offers an indirect but durable cardiovascular centered benefit through not only strengthening cardiac muscles and vessels, but offering a solution similar to gut microbiota diversification mechanisms.

Perhaps the most clinically noteworthy outcome of this review is TMAO's effectiveness as a prognostic biomarker and early indicator for CVD events. Elevated plasma TMAO levels predicted a three-fold increase in heart failure mortality [35], outperformed existing biomarkers in predicting death due to acute myocardial infarction and identified elevated cardiovascular risk in HIV-positive patients with carotid plaques. TMAO's function as a biomarker is not only limited to CVD, as considering recent studies, its relevance in colorectal cancer and neurodegenerative conditions has been highlighted [10,18], suggesting that TMAO may serve as a more widely applicable systemic disease indicator than previously known.

Nonetheless, the precise causal role of TMAO in accelerating atherosclerosis remains debatable, considering the wide gap between laboratory findings and real-life human clinical trials which is yet to be resolved [8,14]. Wide-ranging and more ethnically diverse clinical trials are needed to confirm causation, relevant disease progression and medically established thresholds for interventions. Nevertheless, given that cardiovascular disease

is the leading cause of death globally, accounting for 32% of all deaths worldwide, the integration of TMAO monitoring into an enhanced preventative cardiology framework signifies a highly meaningful and urgent research priority.

13. Appendix and Definitions

Term	Definition
● <i>TMAO</i>	<i>Trimethylamine N-oxide</i> – a metabolite linked to CVD, produced from <i>choline</i> and <i>L-carnitine</i> .
● <i>TMA</i>	<i>Trimethylamine</i> – intermediate metabolite formed in the gut before oxidation to <i>TMAO</i> .
● <i>FMO3</i>	<i>Flavin-containing monooxygenase 3</i> – liver enzyme responsible for oxidizing <i>TMA</i> into <i>TMAO</i> .
● <i>Phosphatidylcholine</i>	A phospholipid found in eggs and soybeans, precursor to <i>TMAO</i> .
● <i>L-carnitine</i>	Nutrient found in red meat, precursor to <i>TMAO</i> .
● <i>Foam cells</i>	Lipid-laden macrophages contributing to atherosclerotic plaque formation.

Term	Definition
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Endothelial dysfunction</i> 	Impaired function of blood vessel lining, leading to vascular disease.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Platelet hyperreactivity</i> 	Increased sensitivity of platelets, promoting clot formation.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Berberine (BBR)</i> 	Plant-derived compound that inhibits <i>TMAO</i> production.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>CutC</i> 	<i>Choline-TMA lyase</i> – bacterial enzyme converting <i>choline</i> to <i>TMA</i> .
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>ADP</i> 	<i>Adenosine diphosphate</i> – platelet agonist involved in clotting.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>HSP</i> 	<i>Heat shock proteins</i> – stress-induced proteins linked to inflammation.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>NF-κB</i> 	<i>Nuclear factor kappa-light-chain-enhancer of activated B cells</i> – signaling pathway involved in inflammation.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>DHA</i> 	<i>Docosahexaenoic acid</i> – omega-3 fatty acid with cardioprotective effects.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>MI</i> 	<i>Myocardial infarction</i> – heart attack.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>HF</i> 	<i>Heart failure</i> .

Term	Definition
● CHD	Coronary heart disease.
● AS	Atherosclerosis.

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